

Effect of rice armyworm *Mythimna separata* (Walker) on grain yield of rice

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A survey conducted in Maligaya, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, showed that farmers (n=100) consider the armyworm (AW) *Mythimna separata* (Walker) one of the most important insect pests of rice during the dry season. The AW hosts include sugar-cane, sorghum, maize, bamboo, and some grasses. At night, AW larvae are actively feeding and cutting rice panicle rachis and stems (see figure). During the day, they are found at the base of tillers.

The occurrence of AW forces some farmers to harvest earlier than scheduled for fear that panicles will be lost. This study quantified the effect of AW on grain yield by comparing healthy hills with hills affected by AW. This information may be used to estimate yield reduction caused by AW.

We studied a 1000-m² farmer's field planted to cultivar IR64 at the rate of 3-4 seedlings hill⁻¹. Fertilizer was applied

Armyworm pupa at the base of tillers and spikelets scattered on the ground as a result of pAW larval feeding. 1996 dry season.

at the rate of 90-30-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹. One week before harvest, 10 plots attacked by AW (at least one panicle lost) and 10 healthy plots measuring 2 × 2 hills plot⁻¹ were marked using 1-m-long bamboo stakes. Two days before harvest, each

plot was harvested to quantify grain yield, total spikelets panicle⁻¹, panicles plot⁻¹, 100-grain weight, and percentage of filled grains.

Results showed about 20% of the panicles clipped by AW. Grain yield of healthy plots differed significantly from that of plots attacked by AW (see table). Reduction in grain yield was less than the percentage of panicles lost due to AW. The AW significantly decreased the number of panicles hill⁻¹ and the number of spikelets panicle⁻¹ but did not affect 100-grain weight or percentage of filled grains.

Further studies should be made to identify the factors influencing the crop-AW system, to determine the extent of AW damage and its economic loss, and to develop means of managing the pest. ■

Grain yield and yield components of plots attacked by armyworm (AW). Maligaya, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1996 DS.

Grain yield or yield component	Healthy hills	Hills attacked by AW	Prob > ITI
Grain weight (g m ⁻²)	458 ± 7.4	379 ± 19.2	0.0012**
Total spikelets (no. panicle ⁻¹)	90.6 ± 1.3	69.4 ± 4.6	0.0003**
100-grain weight (g)	2.55 ± 0.04	2.48 ± 0.03	0.175ns
Total panicles (no. m ⁻²)	388 ± 19.9	309 ± 19.4	0.0115ns
Filled grains (%)	78.2 ± 1.9	75.0 ± 2.3	0.2340ns

Predation of *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker) eggs by the black cricket *Metioche vittaticollis* (Stål)

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Metioche vittaticollis (Stål) is an important predator of rice insect pests, including several defoliators and stem borers. Little information is available about its role in suppressing pest populations.

We studied the predation of *M. vittaticollis* using striped stem borer (SSB) eggs as prey in insect cages. Freshly laid egg masses of SSB were glued to leaves of 35-d-old TN1 rice

plants at densities of 80, 160, 240, 320, and 400 plant⁻¹. These plants were enclosed individually in 11-cm-diam and 55-cm-high cylindrical mylar cages. One *M. vittaticollis*, starved for 12 h, was released for each test plant. Fourth-instar larvae and adult male and female crickets were caged individually with the eggs, and the experiment was replicated 10 times. After 24 h of exposure, the number of eggs consumed at each stage was recorded. Consumption rate per day at each stage of *M. vittaticollis* was determined.

Fourth-instar larvae consumed the highest number of SSB eggs as compared with the other stages of the cricket (Table 1). They fed more than the first three instars combined, probably because of the higher nutri-

tional demands at this late growth stage for developing the reproductive system and flying appendages. Females were more voracious than males. The higher predation rates by the female predator could be attributed to physiological needs for reproduction.

The density response data were fitted to the random predator model
$$Na = n[1 - \exp\{-a(PT - NaTh)\}]$$
 where *Na* is the number of prey attacked, *N* is the density of prey, *a* is the attack rate of the predators, *P* is the number of predators, *Th* is handling time, and *T* is the total time that predator and prey are exposed.

The search parameters, *a* and *Th*, were estimated using the nonlinear curve-fitting procedure PROC NLIN available in SAS (Table 2). In the males,

Table 1. Number of *C. suppressalis* eggs consumed by *M. vittaticollis* for 1 d at a temperature range of 25-30 °C.

Stage	Consumed <i>C. suppressalis</i> eggs (no. d ⁻¹)	
	Mean ± SD ^a	Range
Nymph		
1 st instar	1.7 ± 0.67	1-3
2 nd instar	2.5 ± 0.71	2-4
3 rd instar	13.3 ± 5.58	8-24
4 th instar	184.3 ± 45.2	162-246
Adult		
Male	102.7 ± 23.23	72-147
Female	158.7 ± 53.56	78-246

^a Av of 10 individuals ± SD.

Table 2. Parameter estimates of the functional response equation for *M. vittaticollis* feeding on *C. suppressalis* eggs at a temperature range of 25-30 °C.

Stage	Parameter estimates ^a		Asymptotic SE	
	a	Th	a	Th
4 th -instar nymph	9.9381	0.0037	30.5532	0.0011
Adult male	4.5044	0.0070	4.6008	0.0009
Adult female	4.7314	0.0044	5.3486	0.0009

^a a = attack rate, Th = handling time.

Th was significantly higher, indicating that they have lower feeding capacities than females.

The figure illustrates the relationship between number of SSB eggs attacked and initial egg density. The number of SB eggs attacked by one fourth-instar larva, an adult male, and an adult female increased with prey density. As initial density increased, the consumption of SSB eggs by the cricket increased at a decreasing rate

until a satiation level was reached. The functional response of fourth-instar larva, adult male, and adult female on SSB eggs fitted the Holling's Type II model. This model has also been found to fit the feeding behavior of *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* on planthopper eggs and *Pardosa pseudoannulata* on brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers. ■

Functional response of *M. vittaticollis* on SSB eggs.

Bioassay of *Fusarium pallidoseum* (Cooke) Sacc., (Deuteromycotina: Hyphomycetes) against leaf folder

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Greenhouse studies assessed the pathogenicity of *Fusarium pallidoseum* on rice leaf folder (LF) *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* Guenée at 28.5 °C and between 88 and 90% relative humidity. The pathogen was tested at spore concentrations of 0-1 × 10⁷ conidia mL⁻¹. A stock solution of 1 mL was diluted with sterile distilled water, i.e., 100, 1000, etc., which meant 1 part of the fungus suspension was diluted in 99 or 999 parts of water. Thirty third-instar larvae were dipped for 2 to 3 s in each concentration. Treated larvae were transferred to filter paper and incubated in a petri dish containing fresh rice leaves.

Mortality was determined after 1 wk of incubation and the percentage adjusted using Abbott's formula. Probit analysis

showed that 5.49 × 10³ conidia mL⁻¹ was the effective concentration for LD₅₀ of *F. pallidoseum* (see table). ■

Mortality dose of *F. pallidoseum* on rice leaf folder larvae.

Larvae used (no.)	χ ^{2a}	Slope	LD ₅₀ (conidia mL ⁻¹)	Fiducial limit
180	9.456	0.622	5.49 × 10 ³	2.49 – 12.11 × 10 ³

^aP < 0.05. Heterogeneity analysis: variance = 0.0246. Results of χ² for the above analysis = 13.86719.

Integrated pest management—other pests

Evolving patterns of rat control at IIRI

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This report discusses the changes made at IIRI that have reduced rat problems. A 1987 survey (by N. S. Ahmed and others) indicated that 86% of some 171 field experiments, including 11 trials that were completely lost, suffered rat damage. The lost data were valued at US\$370,000 and the direct cost of con-

trol US\$402,000 (see figure). In 1989, control costs had risen to US\$473,000 but by 1994, they had dropped to US\$52,000, an annual savings of US\$421,000 and lost data costs were also decreased.

Early rat control at IIRI consisted of galvanized iron fences with a single electrified wire at the top. The system had 24-h surveillance by 160 persons involved in rat control. Starting in 1989, an integrated system of rat control, combining six management practices, has led to the dramatic reductions in